

SITE GPR 11	YEAR 2011	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.554 Max: 62.613	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1411 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
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In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1833-1834 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
Tile beneath 1386, located in SE middle part of SU 1411

Covered by SU: 1386 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition
tile floor

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash		
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells		
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass				
			Compaction	Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White
			<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red
			<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts: 1416
Is covered by: 1386	Covers: 1416
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
The tile is all broken, there is a small cluster of tufo to the NW of the tile

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: It is located in the middle of the Southern part of SU 1416

Shape:
It is a polygonal section of tile NOT EXCAVATED 1/20/11

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

Key
 SU 1416 Tile concentration SU 1411

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by KNSU Kaput

on 7/20/11

Revised by CHM

on 29/7/11

PDFd by BCR

on 1/8/11

Entered by

on